

Compliant Deiters' Cells: A Challenge for Outer Hair Cell-based Cochlear Amplification?

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Abstract. Recent experimental evidence of organ of Corti (OoC) vibrations has challenged the traditionally basilar membrane-centric understanding of active cochlear mechanics. There is growing evidence that the main body of the Deiters' Cells (DCs), which sits between the outer hair cells (OHCs) and the basilar membrane (BM), deforms substantially *in vivo*, challenging the notion that the OHC force is directly transmitted to the BM. These findings highlight the need to interpret relative motions within the OoC. This work builds upon a previously developed computational model of the gerbil cochlea containing fluid, structural, and electrical domains. The model contained rigid DCs such that OHC force was directly transmitted to the BM. In this work, the effect of introducing compliance to the DCs is assessed and the degree of compliance of the DCs and OHCs is constrained by comparison to experiments. The results demonstrate that increased compliance of the DCs results in a reduction of nonlinearity in the BM response. A significant amount of cochlear nonlinearity is preserved if the DCs are ~ 10 times stiffer than the OHCs. For a ratio of ~ 3 , nonlinearity can be recovered by increasing the sensitivity of mechano-electrical transduction (MET). In addition, the tonic displacement of the BM, DCs, and RL predicted by the model is compared to experiment, providing further insight on the stiffness of the DCs and OHCs. Overall, the results in this work suggest that compliant DCs do not necessarily eliminate OHC-based amplification of BM traveling waves.

INTRODUCTION

Nonlinearity in cochlear responses is due to force feedback from the outer hair cells (OHCs). Each OHC is sandwiched between the body of a Deiters' cell (DC) and the reticular lamina (RL). The DC bodies (simply referred to as DCs throughout as the phalangeal processes are not considered in this work) terminate at their bottom end at the basilar membrane (BM). While most cochlear models assume that the DCs are very stiff or rigid elements, recent experimental evidence indicates that they may be of comparable compliance to OHCs and much more compliant than the BM [1, 2]. Other recent experimental measurements of OoC mechanical responses have shown broad nonlinearity in the top structures of the OoC [3, 4] in contrast to BM nonlinearity which is localized near the peak region. Collectively, these findings call into question the traditional view that the OHCs efficiently provide a force directly to the BM, which then mediates power delivery to traveling waves in the cochlea.

In this work, we incorporate compliant DCs into our previously developed physiologically motivated cochlear model [5]. We test the effects of compliant DCs on cochlear amplification by comparing results to the previous model, in which the DCs were rigid. We also predict the tonic displacement of various OoC structures and compare to experiment in order to provide additional insight on the stiffness ratios of OoC structures.

MODEL

Physiologically Based Model

Our previously developed, physiologically based model of the gerbil cochlea [5] couples the fluid in the cochlear ducts to the BM, which in turn is coupled to the OoC micromechanical subdomain. The latter contains three degrees of freedom (DOFs) per cross-section to characterize BM, TM-shear, and TM-bending vibrations, respectively. Longitudinal motion is not considered, i.e. the OoC micromechanics are 2-D in the radial-transverse plane. Only the first mode (half-sinusoid) is considered for the BM displacement, and only the BM is coupled to the fluid in the top and bottom ducts (Fig. 1). The fluid within the OoC is neglected. The OHC force, which is regulated by the nonlinear MET current in the electrical subdomain, is transmitted directly to the BM through the rigid DCs (Fig. 1A). In the

FIGURE 1. Physiologically motivated organ of Corti micromechanical model with rigid (A) and compliant (B) DCs. The model in A is the previous micromechanical formulation as found in Samaras et al. [5]. The DCs in B are incorporated as a mechanical DOF that moves in line with the DC-OHC axis. The DC spring K_{dc} opposes their compression/elongation and acts on the BM and the bottom end of the OHCs.

present work, the DC-OHC junction is defined as a fourth micromechanical DOF which defines motion along the OHC/DC axis and which is coupled to the BM via a linear spring (Fig. 1B) in place of the rigid DCs of the original model. This model assumes a massless DC-OHC junction and does not include bending or rotation. As shown in Fig. 1B, the OHC force now acts at its lower end on the DC-OHC junction, and force transmission to the BM is mediated by the DC stiffness (K_{dc}). The model implementation was verified by comparing pure tone responses from the model using the original 3-DOF micromechanical model and the updated 4-DOF model, where the DC stiffness is set to a very large number (such that it is functionally the same as the infinite DC stiffness in the 3-DOF OoC model). The model responses were compared and were effectively identical.

RESULTS

Compliant DCs reduce efficiency but do not eliminate amplification of BM traveling waves

Experiments provide a point of reference for the stiffness of the OHCs and the DCs. OHC somatic stiffness measurements have reported values approximately within 1 and 10 mN/m [6, 7] in the guinea pig apex for OHCs with length of around 60 microns. Assuming that material properties are invariant throughout the cochlea and that K_{ohc} is inversely proportional to cell length, this results in a range of values between 1.5 and 15 mN/m for ~ 40 micron OHCs, which is their approximate length at the 23.5 kHz BP in our model. The value of $K_{ohc} = 6.4$ mN/m (at the 23.5 kHz BP) used in our baseline model with rigid DCs falls within the experimental range. Nam and coworkers [2] constrained the ratio of DC to OHC stiffness between ~ 1 and ~ 10 by fitting a finite element model to patterns of vibrations measured in excised excised gerbil cochleae. In this work, the models with DCs use $K_{ohc} = 25.5$ mN/m (at the 23.5 kHz BP), obtained by increasing baseline K_{ohc} by a factor of 4. From there, K_{dc} is chosen such that $K_{dc}/K_{ohc} = 3$, falling within the range reported in [2].

In the baseline model with rigid DCs, the DCs fully transmit OHC cycle-by-cycle force to the BM. In the model that includes compliant DCs, as the compliance of the DCs is increased, the efficiency of force transmission from the bottom of the OHCs to the BM is reduced. This is demonstrated in Fig. 2, which shows the mechanical responses to a pure tone of the BM, DC-OHC junction, RL, and the ratio of DC to OHC deformation, using linear active and passive formulations of the model. To provide a reference for the models with compliant DCs, the thinner orange lines show the rigid DC model responses. In this case, the DC-OHC junction displacement is the displacement of the BM projected onto the DC-OHC axis, so it is very close in value to the BM displacement (Fig. 2B). Two models with compliant DCs are shown, one with the same MET sensitivity (ratio of HB current to HB deflection) as the rigid DC model and one with increased sensitivity, in lighter and darker blue, respectively. The first of the two models with compliant DCs (lighter blue solid lines) shows reduced active responses in the BM, DC-OHC junction, and RL compression (Fig. 2A-C). The second model in blue has increased MET sensitivity by a factor of 2.4 to recover the BM gain to the value in the baseline model (Fig. 2A, darker blue solid lines). The active peak location of this model is shifted basally in relation to the baseline peak. Notably, even though the active peak of this model has the same amplitude as the BM response of the rigid DC model (Fig. 2A), the DC-OHC junction and RL displacements are greater in magnitude than the baseline (Fig. 2B,C). In the active models with compliant DCs, both without and with increased MET sensitivity, the OHC force equalizes the deformations of the DCs and the OHCs to a ratio close to one at the location of the peak (along vertical dashed line in Fig. 2D).

In the passive model (with compliant DCs), the ratio of DC to OHC deformation in the is 1/3 (dotted line in Fig. 2D), which corresponds to the inverse of $K_{dc}/K_{ohc} = 3$. The two deform in phase (i.e., the DCs and OHCs compress and elongate at the same time, dotted line in Fig. 2H), as the RL moves down when the BM moves up (half-cycle phase difference, dotted blue line in Fig. 2G). There is no external forcing applied at the DC-OHC junction so the DCs and OHCs act as two simple springs in series under load from their opposing ends. On the contrary, when the active OHC force is present, the DC and OHC deformation is roughly out of phase (solid lines in Fig. 2H), such that the DCs now compress when the OHCs elongate and vice-versa.

FIGURE 2. Mechanical responses to a 23.5 kHz pure tone of the model with rigid DCs (orange) and with compliant DCs (blue). The BM, DC-OHC junction, and RL displacement magnitudes (A, B, and C) and phases (E, F, G) are shown. The ratio of DC to OHC deformation (D) and its phase (H) is also shown. Models with compliant DCs use K_{ohc} that is four times the value in the model with rigid DCs and $K_{dc}/K_{ohc} = 3$. Model in lighter blue has same MET sensitivity as the baseline model with rigid DCs; model in darker blue has MET sensitivity increased by a factor of 2.4. Solid and dotted lines are active and passive model responses, respectively. In passive models, the OHC current is set to zero.

Next, we systematically evaluate how the DC and OHC stiffness influence cochlear amplification. For this parametric study, all other model parameters, including MET sensitivity, were kept constant. To quantify cochlear amplification, the BM gain (difference between active and passive model responses to a pure tone at the peak of each, as shown in Fig. 3A) is measured. The surface plot in Fig. 3B shows BM gain as K_{dc} and K_{ohc} are both varied. K_{ohc} and K_{dc} of the models in Fig. 2 are indicated with a white cross. The key trends observed are that there is an upper limit to OHC stiffness (K_{ohc}) and a lower limit to DC stiffness (K_{dc}) beyond which cochlear amplification is eliminated (darkest blue region in surface plot). The two dashed green diagonal lines enclose the region where $1 \leq \frac{K_{dc}}{K_{ohc}} \leq 10$ and show the range of ratios that are comparable to those found in [2]. For the case where $K_{ohc} = 6.4$ mN/m (along the solid horizontal line in Fig. 3B, models within $1 \leq \frac{K_{dc}}{K_{ohc}} \leq 10$ do not exhibit active to passive gain, because K_{dc} is below its previously discussed limit and effectively eliminates force transmission to the BM. For the case where K_{ohc} is increased by a factor of 4 from its baseline value (horizontal dotted line in Fig. 3B), amplification is present within the diagonal lines, but lower than the baseline model. Amplification of the model indicated by the white cross was recoverable by increasing MET sensitivity, as shown previously in Fig. 2. Collectively, the results in Figs. 2 and 3 demonstrate that using DC and OHC stiffness values that are reasonably consistent with experiments, full recovery of cochlear amplification can be obtained if MET sensitivity is increased.

FIGURE 3. Illustration of active to passive gain measurement for the BM response (A). Contour plot of BM active to passive gain for parametric study in which K_{dc} and K_{ohc} are co-varied (B). Active to passive gain is measured at the peak location of each active model. K_{dc} and K_{ohc} values in B are at the 23.5 kHz BP ($x = 0.275$ cm) of the baseline model with rigid DCs. The range of ratios constrained by [2] is indicated in B with dashed green lines. The baseline value of K_{ohc} (6.4 mN/m at the 23.5 kHz BP) and the value that is four times the baseline are indicated with a solid and dashed white line, respectively. The values of K_{dc} and K_{ohc} used in the model with recoverable amplification (dark blue lines in Fig. 2) are indicated with a white cross.

Model with compliant DCs exhibits large tonic displacements

Measurements of tonic displacements provide direct insight on the stiffness relationships within the OoC. The model with rigid DCs and the model with compliant DCs and recovered gain from Fig. 2 are used to predict tonic displacements in the OoC structures. A nonlinear frequency domain algorithm is utilized to predict the zero-frequency harmonic (i.e., the tonic displacement) in addition to the primary frequency response to a pure tone at 60 dB SPL. The results are compared to the RL, DC/OHC junction, and BM waveforms measured in [1], which are shown in Fig. 4 A, E, and I, respectively. This experiment shows relatively large tonic displacements of -4.5 nm and 12.5 nm on the RL and DC/OHC junction, respectively, and a much smaller tonic displacement of 1.3 nm on the BM. As the RL deviates towards the scala tympani and the DC-OHC junction towards the scala vestibuli, the OHCs and the DCs exhibit a constant compression and elongation, respectively. The two models show an RL response with a tonic displacement that is consistent in magnitude and direction (towards scala tympani) with the experiment, as seen in Fig. 2B and C, and so capture the experimentally observed OHC compression. In the rigid DC model, the DC-OHC junction displacement (Fig. 4E) is identical to the BM displacement (Fig. 4H) and exhibits a very small tonic displacement of 0.4 nm (towards scala vestibuli). The model with compliant DCs and recovered gain exhibits a tonic displacement of 9 nm in the DC/OHC junction (Fig. 2F), which is roughly consistent in magnitude with the experimentally observed tonic displacement (Fig. 2D) and also matches the direction towards the scala vestibuli. This model also exhibits a BM tonic displacement of 0.5 nm (Fig. 4I), which is roughly a third of the experimentally measured value (Fig. 4G).

DISCUSSION

This work demonstrates that a model with compliant DCs that deform along their axial direction and power delivery to the traveling wave only through BM-fluid coupling is compatible with cochlear amplification. However, the important caveat that sensitivity of MET transduction must be increased substantially to recover the BM gain to its value in the rigid DC model must be considered. This calls into question the efficacy of power delivery to the traveling wave from the OHCs via compliant DCs, but this mechanism is nevertheless a possibility in our model. Using values of K_{ohc} and K_{dc} that are constrained by those found in experiments, the tonic displacements predicted by the model compare well in both magnitude and direction with experimental ones.

Another potential pathway for power delivery from the OHCs to the BM is via the pillar cells. These are known to be effectively rigid (in comparison to other OoC structures), and therefore can transmit the force from the top of the OHCs to the BM via their attachment point to the RL. Increased stiffness of the attachment of the RL to the top of the

FIGURE 4. Waveforms of the RL (A, B, and C), DC-OHC junction (D, E, and F) and BM (G, H, and I) in experiment (left), model with rigid DCs (middle), and with compliant DCs and recovered gain (right). Experiment from [1] is near-CF response to a 9 kHz stimulus at 60 dB SPL, measured in the apex of the mouse cochlea. Models are near-CF responses to a 23.5 kHz stimulus at 60 dB SPL.

pillar cells (K_{rl} in Fig. 1) can increase power delivery to the BM via the pillar cell pathway. In turn, this alternate pillar cell pathway can facilitate traveling wave amplification near-BF instead of (or in addition to) the pathway via the DCs. Further potential limitations of the model are the lack of phalangeal processes and bending/rotation of the DC-OHC junction, both of which may be critical in characterizing the experimentally observed longitudinal component in OoC motion [8]. Whether this motion plays a key role in cochlear amplification remains to be seen. In addition, the greater vibrations of the top of the OoC compared to the BM shift into focus the possibility of power delivery to the traveling wave via the top surface of the OoC in addition to the BM, as studied by Altoè and co-workers in [9]. Future work includes incorporating the phalangeal processes and representing longitudinal motion in the micromechanics, as well as studying the implications of coupling both the BM and the top of the OoC to the intracochlear fluid.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This research is funded by NIH grant R01DC016114 and NSF grant CMMI2309953.

REFERENCES

1. J. B. Dewey, A. Altoè, C. A. Shera, B. E. Applegate, and J. S. Oghalai, "Cochlear outer hair cell electromotility enhances organ of corti motion on a cycle-by-cycle basis at high frequencies in vivo," *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **118** (2021).
2. W. Zhou, T. Jabeen, S. Sabha, J. Becker, and J.-H. Nam, "Deiters cells act as mechanical equalizers for outer hair cells," *Journal of Neuroscience* **42**, 8361–8372 (2022).

3. W. He, D. Kemp, and T. Ren, "Timing of the reticular lamina and basilar membrane vibration in living gerbil cochleae," *eLife* **7**, e37625 (2018).
4. J. B. Dewey, B. E. Applegate, and J. S. Oghalai, "Amplification and suppression of traveling waves along the mouse organ of corti: evidence for spatial variation in the longitudinal coupling of outer hair cell-generated forces," *Journal of Neuroscience* **39**, 1805–1816 (2019).
5. G. Samaras, H. Wen, and J. Meaud, "Broad nonlinearity in reticular lamina vibrations requires compliant organ of corti structures," *Biophysical Journal* **122**, 880–891 (2023).
6. J. A. Tolomeo, C. R. Steele, and M. C. Holley, "Mechanical properties of the lateral cortex of mammalian auditory outer hair cells," *Biophysical Journal* **71**, 421–429 (1996).
7. D. Z. He and P. Dallos, "Properties of voltage-dependent somatic stiffness of cochlear outer hair cells," *Journal of the Association for Research in Otolaryngology* **1**, 64–81 (2000).
8. N. P. Cooper, A. Vavakou, and M. van der Heijden, "Vibration hotspots reveal longitudinal funneling of sound-evoked motion in the mammalian cochlea," *Nature Communications* **9**, 1–12 (2018).
9. A. Altoë, J. B. Dewey, K. K. Charaziak, J. S. Oghalai, and C. A. Shera, "Overturning the mechanisms of cochlear amplification via area deformations of the organ of corti," *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America* **152**, 2227–2239 (2022).
10. T. Bowling, H. Wen, S. W. F. Meenderink, W. Dong, and J. Meaud, "Intracochlear distortion products are broadly generated by outer hair cells but their contributions to otoacoustic emissions are spatially restricted," *Scientific Reports* **11**, 13651 (2021).
11. W. He and T. Ren, "The origin of mechanical harmonic distortion within the organ of corti in living gerbil cochleae," *Communications Biology* **4**, 1–11 (2021).
12. A. Macic and J.-H. Nam, "Organ of corti kinematic gain in mouse and gerbil cochlea," *Mechanics of Hearing Workshop 2024* (2024).
13. A. Fridberger, I. Tomo, M. Ulfendahl, and J. Boutet de Monvel, "Imaging hair cell transduction at the speed of sound: dynamic behavior of mammalian stereocilia," *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **103**, 1918–1923 (2006).

COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[*Online Forum*]

[Wen Cai]: Hi George. I have two questions for you. (1) Do you have any explanation for the spikes in Fig.2 (D) and Fig.2 (H)? It seems like when you increase the sensitivity to recover the gain, there are always some spikes. (2) What is the value you used for the MET sensitivity? Is the MET sensitivity the only influential factor in recovering the gain?

[George Samaras]: Regarding the spikes in Fig. 2 D and H, these are due to the notch observed in the mechanical responses at around $x=0.2$ cm. This notch is in some way an antiresonance present in the active response of the model with compliant Deiters' Cells (DCs) and recovered gain. This notch can be reduced or eliminated by adjusting model parameters. For the model with rigid DCs (orange lines in Fig. 2), the MET sensitivity is the same as that listed in the supplemental info of [5]. The model with compliant DCs in lighter blue also uses this same MET sensitivity, while the recovered gain model (darker blue) uses an MET sensitivity that is 2.4 times that of the baseline model.

[Brian Frost]: Hi George - I appreciate your work, and especially enjoyed your talk. I had two questions/comments. 1) The cochlear micromechanics model you show in the figures is 2-D, and I think this needs to be more explicitly stated in the work. I don't think it's a weakness of the model necessarily, but 2) without longitudinal space, I am not sure how your model maintains conservation of fluid mass. Is it by letting cortilymph "escape" into the scalae? If so, again, that's fine, but definitely deserves an explanation (especially considering the works of Altoe and Guinan).

[George Samaras]: I think that understanding the role of the DCs is critical for understanding how the mechanics mediate cochlear amplification so I am also glad that you (and others) are looking at them experimentally. Regarding your questions: 1.) This is a great point - the cochlear micromechanics in our model are 2-D (i.e. no longitudinal motion). 2.) The current model does not include cortilymph - we only model the fluid in the top and bottom ducts and couple it to the BM only.

[Yanli Wang]: Hi George, nice work! I especially appreciated that the model could predict a tonic displacement in the RL and DC/OHC junction observed in the experiments. Following are some comments: 1) could you comment on the "kinks" observed in Fig 2 darker blue line (compliant DC with enhanced MET sensitivity) in various panels? For example, a small region of phase lead is seen in Fig 2E. 2) Fig 3, could you add explanation of dotted and solid white lines in the figure legend (I found them in the text). Could you also highlight the region where Kohc is reasonable within the experimental range? 3) This may have been included in previous work, I am also curious how much did the bundle move in your model with compliant and rigid DCs? How does this value compare with experimental data? (kinematic gain? See [12] and its references)

[George Samaras]: 1.) Regarding the "kinks" in Fig. 2, this is a result of the fact that the active response of that model exhibits an antiresonance in the region right before the peak. It is possible to eliminate this by changing the

mechanical parameters of the model such that the active peak is more apical relative to the passive peak. 3.) In general in our models (with stiff or compliant DCs), hair bundle deflection depends on the relative motion between the RL and TM. I find that the HB deflection is roughly 10 dB lower (~ 3 times smaller) than the RL motion, which is consistent with [13].

[Post-talk Q&A]

[Jont Allen]: What is the membrane capacitance of the Deiters' cells? You have the same problem that the outer hair cells have which is a low-pass filtering effect so you don't get any cycle-by-cycle gain if the capacitance is too large.

[George Samaras]: The Deiters' cells are passive though, they are just transmitting the outer hair cell force.

[Sebastian Meenderink]: On what do you base this assumption that the pillar cells are very stiff and can transmit this force? Maybe it's better to preempt your previous models of the Deiters' cells and replace them [the pillar cells] with springs and see what happens there.

[George Samaras]: The rigid pillar cells is something we assume in our model. I am not sure what the experimental evidence says but to my understanding the pillar cells are pretty rigid.

[Sebastian Meenderink]: That's what I am saying, that's what you assumed for the Deiters' cells but then you replaced them with springs.

[George Samaras]: That's a possibility (to also replace the pillar cells with springs), thank you.

[Lisa Olson]: Number one, the pillar cells are stiff, I measured that with Dick Mountain. I really liked the way your model developed. I think your final results with the RL having a higher amplitude in the best frequency region but not as much increase in the sub-BF region is consistent with a lot of the transverse data which gets to the question of looking at longitudinal versus transverse motion in these models, which will be an important next step.

[George Samaras]: I understand that the sub-BF nonlinearity in the reticular lamina is a point of contention, I'm not sure how that contextualizes our results.

[Rob Raphael]: Two quick questions, one is did you match the Dewey data just with the parameters that you had or did you have to play with the parameters?

[George Samaras]: I didn't play with them very much. There are things we can do to improve things [agreement with data] but I don't know if there's too much value in that, just to try to match experimental results exactly.

[Rob Raphael]: Second question is, you modeled the Deiters' cells as a stiff element. Years ago Robert Patuzzi and Chadwick were talking about the viscosity of the Deiters' cell, which hasn't been measured. How would that change things if you gave the Deiters' cells some viscoelastic parameters?

[George Samaras]: That's a good question, because that would presumably change the phase relationship [which could affect OHC force transmission to the BM via the DCs] if I added a viscous element in the Deiters' cells as well, so that's something to consider.

[Catalina Velez-Ortega]: Good data, I think you already answered my question, you haven't had time to play with the data yet. But I was wondering if you could try to change slightly the stiffness of the pillar cells. They are stiffer but we do have some experimental data that after an increase in calcium, intracellularly, they contract slowly and remain contracted, so maybe increasing the stiffness to test what they would do to your model.

[George Samaras]: The rigid pillar cells are a model assumption we have currently but making those stiff spring elements is something we could look into. [If the pillar cells are stiff spring elements, they would likely result in similar model responses as when they are rigid.]

[Aleks Zosuls]: I just want to jump on the membrane capacitance thing again. A lot of times we think of the membrane capacitance of an individual hair cell. If you put them all in a group, you're effectively decreasing the surface area. If you look at a basal turn where they're packed together, is the capacitance somehow reduced spatially, which would probably cause an issue with prestin and voltage change.

[Alessandro Altoe]: How much would the tectorial membrane have to move in your model? It has to be not moving much I guess.

[George Samaras]: In general in our model, the TM transverse displacement is similar to that of the reticular lamina.